

EVALUATING BY EXPERIENCE THE ROLE OF TEACHERS AND TUTORS IN DISTANCE LEARNING EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The distance learning paradigm is currently being considered as an effective alternative to promote “education for all” on a worldwide basis. The objective of this paper is to evaluate by experience the role of teachers, tutors and other relevant actors in distance learning courses. The proposed approach is to define a distribution model for the teacher’s skills in the new distance learning scenario, to identify new actors, to map tasks associated with the learning process to the actors and, finally, to identify profiles and discuss relevant abilities for maximizing course quality. ICT resources is an important component considered in the overall discussion and the implementation scenario considered is an undergraduate level course for active high-school teachers requiring certification for improving their pedagogical methods. In effect, the model, the numbers and the implementation aspects highlighted are based on a real-life ongoing course.

1. THE DISTANCE LEARNING SCENARIO

Education is being considered as a major challenge for the developing countries since, only with social projects oriented to the individual’s educational and cultural enrichment, development can be sustained. Being so, professional qualification in a broader sense becomes a challenge for all.

In this permanent educational scenario, there is the need to balance individual’s available time in a more efficient manner and to reconsider the notion of “space” for studying. Learners, teachers and other actors in the learning process do not have anymore to be in the same physical location and, beyond that, the learning process must extrapolate the conventional F2F (face-to-face) classroom concepts and boundaries.

The distance learning paradigm is, apparently, an effective alternative to promote education in a broader and scalable perspective. As such, the role of teachers, tutors and other relevant actors in the learning process has to be carefully investigated, experienced and evaluated in order to, eventually, obtain or converge to an integration model that could couple with the current worldwide educational needs.

2. (RE) SEARCHING FOR A MODEL

(Re)Searching a model for distance learning has become a very common activity in universities, research and governmental institutions worldwide. Typically, these institutions have created not only pilot and/or experimental courses but also research groups focused on the problem investigation. In general, there is strong focus on the teaching-learning strategy with a trend to consider it as a dual-sense relation which effectively influences the overall result obtained in the learning process.

As an example of “searching models”, the initial option adopted in Brazil by most of the institutions was to offer undergraduate courses focused on “lectures formation” (Portuguese language, mathematics, science, biology and chemistry are examples of courses massively created). Following this initial trend, it is observed the offer of postgraduate courses (*lato sensu*) targeting to provide specialization and qualification for professionals in a broad sense.

Distance learning activities have evolved, and this is an important information to consider:

- Distance learning courses and/or research groups have been created by 70 institutions (2004).

- The evolution in terms of institutions involved with distance learning is as follows: 10 (2001), 16 (2002), 46 (2003).
- Students currently engaged in distance learning programs: above 100.000
- Offered annual entries: about 17.000 (governmental institutions only)

For all these institutions one of the main challenges is to create a new model for distance learning. There is an effective demand for qualified professionals and training strategies capable of dealing with this new paradigm and the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) resources (DECINA, 1997). The associated investment for distance learning courses is considerable and, as such, research or experimental results may contribute to reduce the barriers associated with the offer of new courses.

2.1 The regulation and quality issues

Regulation and course quality are very important issues in the new distance learning scenario. In effect, some countries have used regulation as a strategy to keep distance learning course quality at nationwide level.

In Brazil, the Ministry of Education (MEC) through law 9394 (*Lei de Diretrizes e Bases da Educação de 1996*) and act 2492/ 1998 has regulated the offer of distance learning courses by defining directives for courses using ICT resources and virtual interaction. In brief, it defines the distance learning courses as follows:

“An alternative to offer courses which employs self-learning, with the mediation of course contents and pedagogical resources systematically organized, offered through different media, used isolated or in combination and distributed by alternative communications media.”

The accreditation process created was the effective way to promote distance learning course quality and to avoid misunderstandings and abuses. Although restrictive, the accreditation process played an important role by reducing the criticism and reluctance in adopting offered distance learning courses in substitution to F2F ones.

3. THE “TEACHER’S SKILLS” DISTRIBUTION MODEL

The first step in the following discussion consists in defining a distribution model for teacher’s skills. In this context, an effective real-life experience (pilot course) is considered a consistent way to exercise the understanding of how teachers and learners interact and their roles for distance learning education. As such, the herein assumptions and discussions are based on a pilot project as described (MARTINS, 2004):

- Undergraduate course: Portuguese and English Language (2.940 hours – 03 years).
- Course coverage: state of Bahia (Brazil), 198 provinces (about 2.000 Km range), most of them with very difficult terrestrial access and very limited ICT and computational facilities.
- Attendee’s profile: 500 students, most of them beyond 40 years, active lectures on various teaching subjects at secondary governmental local schools, having very limited computer abilities.

First of all, it seems to exist a consensus among authors, but not for all, that teacher’s competence and presence at class (F2F and virtual) is an important requirement for the learning process. It is also agreed that teacher’s role in either virtual or conventional F2F scenarios may varies considerably and, as such, it is necessary a more precise understanding of what actors are involved and what are their interactions in terms of the learning process.

In F2F conventional classrooms (KEETON, 2002) there is a well-know set of actors and interactions. In brief, the learning process is mainly supported and conducted by the teacher with a more general pedagogical supervision executed by, typically, a pedagogical coordinator. This is a rather common and well accepted structure used for supporting the F2F conventional learning process (Figure 1).

The learning process must be somehow reconfigured when adopting the distance learning approach. The reconfiguration of the learning process consists essentially in the following steps:

- The identification of the actors (new and conventional ones) involved in the process;
- The mapping of the tasks associated to each one of the actors; and
- The identification of the required profiles and abilities which are necessary to support the assigned roles in the new scenario.

Figure 1 – F2F actors and interactions in conventional classrooms

One proposed approach to help the understanding of the various possible alternatives that are nowadays being researched worldwide for the distance learning paradigm is to consider the distribution of the teacher’s skills currently used in conventional F2F classrooms.

The figure 2 illustrates a scenario with a set of suggested actors involved in a distance learning course and represents the distribution model proposed for the teacher’s skills in this new learning paradigm. In effect, this model is being used in the pilot project previously mentioned and identifies the main relations with respect to conventional teacher’s responsibilities and skills.

Figure 2 – Teacher’s skills distribution model

The main aspects and changes to consider in the distance learning paradigm with respect to the teacher’s skills used in F2F are as follows:

- The teacher remains as the main component of the learning process with an overall and eventual hierarchical control of the course as a whole;
- Tutors and/or monitors are present in the distribution model as the component between the teacher and the students/ learners;
- Students/ learners in this distribution model are typically geographically distributed and may scale to very large numbers;
- Course contents production in the distribution model may eventually be “outsourced” in terms of the teacher’s skills;
- The coordination process in this distribution model may eventually be broken into different coordination activities and functionalities (pedagogical, executive, other) impacting and interacting with teacher’s basic skills.

As suggested in figure 2, one of the main premises adopted by the proposed model is the preservation of teacher’s hierarchical and orchestration role for all activities in the distance learning course. Effectively, the inter-relations between the various actors became more complex with respect to F2F scenarios but the basic “conducting role” of the teacher is kept.

Tutors and/or monitors are new actors introduced in the distribution model to deal with two basic and very important issues:

- The distance between teachers and students/ learners.
- The scaling problem.

As far as the scaling problem is concerned, tutors play a fundamental role. Since the social, economics and budgetary aspects of distance learning courses typically require both a huge number of students which typically have a geographically widespread distribution, there is a fundamental need for assistance either locally or virtually. In brief, tutors interact with students on behalf of the teacher wherever they are and, effectively, assume part of the F2F classical class conducting interactions eventually existent in conventional courses. The conducting attributions are such as answering questions and enforcing student’s attention to the developed subject, among others.

The coordination process in the proposed distribution model is split into different activities such as:

- A pedagogical coordination which deals with the general pedagogical aspects of the course as a whole.
- An executive coordination which deals with the operational problems typically occurring in distance learning courses such as logistics and human resources articulation, among others.
- An “integration matrix coordination” that will specifically explore and articulate the interdisciplinary methods between the learning units used in the distance learning course as proposed in MARTINS (2002).

In terms of the interactions between actors, the teacher’s skills distribution model proposes a far more complex structure with respect to F2F scenario (Figures 01 and 02). First of all, the number and the type of actors involved are considerably augmented and this represents a real challenge for the teacher general abilities. In the proposed model for distance learning courses the interactions are considered independently and are articulated by the teacher with coordination support. The following discussion describes these relations and other operational aspects for course implementation.

First, a significant number of tutors/ monitors are involved in the learning process. The number adopted scales linearly with the number of students engaged in the specific program. Typical choices for the relation tutor/ students range from 1/20 to 1/100. Factors like the functionality and profile adopted for the tutor and the technical scope of the course itself influence the definition of the relation tutor/ student. Experience shows that this option is very important for both the quality and financial health of the course.

The teacher interaction with students must be preserved in this model but is effectively an indirect relation. In this sense, ICT resources must play an important role. The proposed distribution model assumes that, on execution, ICT resources must be used to guarantee a minimal and efficient set of interactions between teacher and students. For instance, video-conferencing and other broadcasting facilities might be used to allow some scaling in the process of contacting and interacting with students.

The interaction with the coordinators (pedagogical, executive and interdisciplinary) is less complex but equally important. In effect, the structure is proposed with the objective of allowing scaling for the

coordination process itself. The teacher's abilities in this case are necessary to articulate different perspectives of the course such as the pedagogical aspects, the operational aspects and the interdisciplinary aspect.

Finally, the teacher has eventually to deal with an "outsourced" contents developed by another specialist in the subject. In the proposed distribution model, the course contents development may be developed by the teacher itself or not. In practical and effective terms, it is always suggested to the teacher that he should invest a certain amount of preparation time developing the course as the most effective and the best solution. In case it does not happen that way, the teacher must adapt himself to the developed material. In this second scenario, the preparation of the course contents leaves always some room for "course personalization" for instance, in terms of the interdisciplinary activities or practical exercises and, as such, the course preparation become more oriented to adjust and adapt methods and exercises for the students.

4. EVALUATING BY EXPERIENCE THE CHALLENGES FOR "TEACHERS AND LEARNERS" AT INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY (ICT) AGE

The distribution of teacher's skills and abilities, as proposed in the distribution model, is a challenging task. In effect, the real-life changes and challenges for the teachers are:

- Teacher's conventional role is effectively distributed and shared among different actors requiring a new set of interactions.
- Teachers must assume different roles in teaching.
- Pedagogical skills are an absolute must for teachers.
- ICT skills are necessary for teachers.
- Planning is a requirement for teachers and an essential must in distance learning programs.

Next, these changes and challenges are discussed based on the acquired experience from the distance learning course mentioned in section 3 and, beyond that, the focus will be on trying to discuss an identify a typical profile for the actors involved with a stronger emphasis on teacher and tutors.

4.1 Evaluating by experience the teacher's profile for distance learning programs

Teacher's profile for distance learning programs following the proposed model requires a set of characteristics that are now discussed.

First, "conventional teachers" (F2F) need to reflect about their professional attitude and eventually required changes. By observing how this was happening with educators and being an effective obstacle to them, PERRENOUD (1998, p. 19) wrote: "the inertia is strong at structural level, in texts and, mainly, in minds, so that a new idea could not prevail rapidly"¹. Other authors assume a proactive position by saying that Internet is perfect for unquiet teachers, which are receptive to news and which intend to update themselves and to communicate in a more efficient way. This shows that changes in pedagogical approaches and projects are imperative. As such, "creativity" may represent the differential for each teacher and may also become an asset to survive in a so competitive scenario.

In the model proposed, the teacher is not any more the "owner of the knowledge" and, as such, needs to exercise aspects such as:

- The reuse of contents and experiences provided by the students.
- To substitute individual actions, mainly present in F2F scenarios, by auto-sufficient, participative and integrating actions.
- To promote the interdisciplinary methods in more creative formats and effective media, eventually using massively ICT resources as a fundamental tool to achieve the learning objectives.
- To share his autonomy, one of the most important assets for F2F teachers, on behalf of other actors involved in the learning process.
- To work in a multidisciplinary fashion, attracting various areas and competences on behalf of his own course/ program.
- To share and negotiate decisions with the involved actors, promoting interaction and efficiency for the learning process.

The teacher has also to adopt the new ICT paradigm as an effective tool in the learning process. Beyond that, the teacher must perceive “how” he will work with it and “how” he will behave and position himself in class (virtual). The teacher predisposition to learn is a fundamental requirement in a broad sense and, in effect, this pre-condition is one of the most important aspects to work in distance learning programs. Also, it observed that once capacitated in ICT resources the resistance to new methods in considerably reduced.

Another aspect in relation to the teacher profile is his understanding and granting about class controls. In distance learning scenarios teacher’s control are typically managed by the distance learning platform which is far more efficient than the classical F2F controls (presence lists and class diary, for instance).

With respect to ICT resources and more technical characteristics required when working in the distance learning paradigm, the teacher needs:

- To promote and integrate students through group tasks, forums and chats.
- To promote assimilation of contents through ICT tools.
- To be effective in answering student’s questions or, in other words, to answer students as fast as possible. Typically, some institutions have these “answering metrics” established as contractual parameters (for instance, maximum time to answer student’s questions).
- To elaborate evaluations that preserves the distance learning characteristics.

In terms of the teacher style, the following aspects are important (LIBÂNEO apud Munhoz, 1988):

- To assume and mediate the students active learning process.
- To know and exercise strategies to teach thinking and to learn learning.
- To promote a critical and reflexive learning among students.
- To preserve the cultural diversity and differences in virtual classes.

Planning is a crucial aspect in distance learning courses. The course contents have to be fully prepared *a priori* and this is an important factor of success. There is no room for improvisation (a component eventually present in F2F scenario) and the teacher abilities and style should be focused on promoting the course dynamics and helping students having difficulties either with ICT resources or course contents.

4.2 Evaluating by experience the tutor’s profile for distance learning programs

Tutors in the distribution model proposed may have two different styles of interaction with students:

- Virtual interaction or
- F2F interaction.

The virtual interaction is realized by the so called “virtual tutor”. It is an alternative where the contacts among students and tutors are mainly supported by the distance learning platform. In this specific case, F2F contacts are implemented by “integration moments” that corresponds to regularly promoted meetings with a timing scheduled define according with course contents and characteristics. The important aspect to observe is that the proposed model defines the possibility of using ICT resources to support the tutoring activities.

The tutoring activities supporting F2F interaction corresponds to a second alternative which is the more commonly used. In this case, tutors and students are physically close and interact on a more constant and frequent basis. For this particular alternative, the tutor is also named “monitor” just to differentiate among the different tutoring styles used.

In the model adopted the tutor (or monitor) is positioned closed to the student. Among the various important tasks assigned to this professional, it is included:

- The tutor should help the teacher in the learning process.
- The tutor should support student’s needs in a broad sense.

The tutors in the distribution model proposed are specialized. In other words, tutors dominate, to some extent, the specific knowledge corresponding to the discipline/ module he is in charge. These characteristics create a delicate balance between teachers and tutors but, additionally, it is a valuable resource in promoting the learning process and, as suggested before, it promotes a more efficient distribution of the teacher’s skills on behalf of the learners.

Beyond that and according with the distribution model, the tutors profile is such that:

- Tutors should be trained in distance learning and ICT tools to adequately support and answer student's technical questions.
- Tutors should also be capacitated in pedagogical skills to more adequately promote the pedagogical requirements for the course.
- Tutors should be flexible.
- Tutors should avoid the student "isolation" that is one of the main causes of evasion in distance learning courses.

Other characteristics for the tutoring work in the proposed model are:

- To keep student's motivation and interest in the course contents.
- To have good communication attributes.
- To instigate student's creativity and self-learning abilities.

In brief, it is necessary that tutors implement motivational strategies focused on a referential set like: the stimulus of student's activities, the indication of complementary lectures, the systematic help in interpreting and understanding course contents, the stimulus to collaborative learning among students, the use of a clear conversational language and the substitution of "dry" texts by a richer set of studying resources on behalf of learners.

Some case studies about distance learning courses point out that an inadequate tutoring support might be a major source of problems. In effect, untrained or inadequate tutor profile may result in transferring to students some insecurity and promoting evasion.

4.3 Other actors involved

In the distribution model proposed, the students have a more active perspective as far as they are also responsible for their own learning. Differently from F2F scenario, students are not necessarily conducted by the teacher. In distributing the teacher's skills, both teacher and tutors mediate the learning process not necessarily indicating "what", "where" and "how" they could learn. In other words, students are active in learn learning.

Collaborative learning supported by teachers, tutors, ICT resources and computers is a prominent asset in this strategy and, as a result, all actors effectively learn in the process.

The course coordinators interact mainly with the teacher and, to a smaller extent, with the tutors. The strategy adopted in the distribution model by splitting the coordination process in different and specific tasks is focused on facilitating course implementation by specializing in different actors the pedagogical, executive and integration tasks.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A model for distributing teacher's skills in distance learning courses and the actors, tasks, required profiles and abilities associated with this model have been briefly described. It is argued that a clearer understanding of the role for teachers, tutors and other actors in distance learning courses is a fundamental question that will increase the offer of new courses and will promote education on a scalable basis. It is also argued that the teacher may keep his conventional role in distance learning courses, but his abilities and skills have to be readapted and/ or reorganized. In particular, the interaction among actors orchestrated by the teacher is an important aspect to consider. In addition, it is also argued that the pedagogical skills are fundamental and, when associated with ICT resources, may provide the means for improve and maximize course quality.

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